

**Office bearers of
GCT78**

President:

H Ramalingam, Managing
Director, Shri Ramana Group
of Industries, Chennai, India

Vice Presidents:

G Mohana Prakasha
Energy Solution

M Markandan
CAD/CAE Solution

Treasurer:

N Vasantha Sekaran
Director, Shri Ramana Group
of Industries, Chennai, India

Secretary:

P Purushothaman,
Director, Centre for
University Industry
Interaction, Periyar
Maniammai University,
Vallam, Thanjavur,
India, Pin 613 403
Web: www.pmu.edu,
email: dircuui@pmu.edu,
editor.ijareep@gmail.com

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ACTION RESEARCH AND ENGINEERING TO ERADICATE POVERTY – IJAREEP

A PUBLICATION OF GCT78

BOARD OF EDITORS (CONSULTING):

CHIEF – EDITOR : Dr. THANDAVAMOORTHY K, DIRECTOR, LIBRARY,
PERIYAR MANIAMMAI UNIVERSITY, INDIA

Mr. PURUSHOTHAMAN P, AS SECRETARY OF GCT78

Dr. NALLATHAMBI P, ENGINEERING CONSULTANT, AUSTRALIA

Dr. CHELLAMUTHU K C, SPECIALIST IN ICT, USA

Dr. RAVICHANDRAN P, ANNAMALAI UNIVERSITY, INDIA

Dr. GABRIEL M, PERIYAR MANIAMMAI UNIVERSITY, INDIA

GCT78 AS A BODY ACCEPTS NO RESPONSIBILITY FOR STATEMENTS MADE BY INDIVIDUALS.

REPRINTS OF ANY PORTION OF THE PUBLICATION MAY BE MADE PROVIDED THAT REFERENCE THERETO BE QUOTED.

Original Articles or papers on any topic are invited which can be submitted to editor by email. However, authors may have to add a foot-note by reflecting on how their work can reduce poverty or mention or propose on further research or interventions to reduce poverty. Authors are required to pay Rs. 500/- per article towards cost of printing, distribution and incidental (above 5 pages, Rs 100 per page extra is required to be paid)

A refereed research journal on Engineering and Humanities

OFFICE ADDRESS FOR COMMUNICATION: GCT78, AP 769, DOOR-53, STREET-59,
SECTOR-10, K K NAGAR, CHENNAI- 600 078, INDIA,
TELEFAX: +91-44-2366 2346 CELL PHONE +91-94443 85195,
EMAIL: editor.ijareep@gmail.com

PRINTER AND PUBLISHER: PURUSHOTHAMAN P, ON BEHALF OF GCT78, K K NAGAR, CHENNAI,
PRINTED AT OFFSET PRINTERS SRI RENUKA ENTERPRISE, CHENNAI

POST YOUR DISCUSSIONS / FEEDBACK TO :

editor.ijareep@gmail.com, editor@ijareep.org

www.ijareep.org

ISSN 2229-5259

*International Journal Of Action
Research And Engineering To
Eradicate Poverty:*
Vol.2, No.5. May 2011.

Contributors:

PAN 057 – Editors

PAN 058 – Latha J. K.

Pp – 370 - 374

PAN 059 – Kasinathan J., et. al

Pp – 375 - 380

PAN 060 – Manjunatha K., et. al

Pp – 381 - 386

PAN 061 – Natarajan K., et. al

Pp – 387 - 391

PAN 062 – Purushothaman P., et. al

Pp – 392 - 396

PAN 063 – Meenakshi Sundaram P., et. al

Pp – 397 - 407

PAN 064 – Raju K., et. al

Pp – 408 - 418

Advertiser :

Shri Ramana Group of Companies,
Chennai, www.shriramana.com

Date & Place of publication:

15th May, 2011

Chennai-600078

Editorial

In this edition, we have a paper on ICT consumers in special libraries: reshaping the information demand highlighting the user trends. A paper on Web-based resources catering to the needs of various scientific fraternity on cosmetic and personal care. Third paper on a study of scholar's behaviour on IR. Fourth paper is on study of consumer behaviours related to tyre-replacement of automobiles. Fifth paper on a case study for online survey of training need analysis of unskilled construction workers. Sixth paper on development of a conceptual tool for testing of software projects. Seventh paper on an activity-theory-based model to analyse web application requirements provides Web application developers with a model that allows them to properly specify navigational and organizational requirements.

We are happy to extend the last date for receipt of papers for special issue to 15th June 2011.

Editors

Impact of experience towards purchase of replacement tyres in light and heavy commercial vehicles

Natarajan K.

Assistant Professor of Business Administration
Directorate of Distance Education, Annamalai University, Tamilnadu
natrajselvi@gmail.com

Soundararajan K.

Associate Professor of Business Administration,
Directorate of Distance Education, Annamalai University, Tamilnadu

A wide range of factors create customer expectations. A customer's previous experiences, the communication of an organisation with its customers, advertisements, service recovery, promises, informal recommendations, formal recommendations, price to be paid, personal needs, corporate image and sales people all influence the formation of customer expectations. Out of these factors, customers experience also influence more on replacement of tyres in Light and Heavy commercial Vehicles. This paper analyse how the experience plays as a major role in tyre-replacement segment of commercial vehicles.

Keywords: Replacement, Tyre, Commercial Vehicles, Customer

Introduction:

Basic psychology process play an important role in understanding how consumers actually make their buying decision and the key interest to the marketers is the major information sources to which the consumer will turn and the relative influence each will have in the subsequent purchase decision. These information sources fell into four groups. (1) Personal – family, friends, neighbours, acquaintances. (2) Commercial – Advertising, web sites, sales persons, dealers, packaging, displays. (3) Public – man media, consumer – rally organization. (4) Experiential – Handling, examining, uses the product. Though gathering information, the consumer learns about competing brands and their features. Some brands will meet initial buying criteria, as the consumer gathers more information's, only a few will remain strong contenders. The consumer makes a final choice from a set.

Replacement market is one of the more sought-after markets by Tyre players, since the margins are better compared to those of OEM's (Original Equipment Manufacturers) who are relatively few in number and have a huge bargaining power. Replacement demand, which comes from existing automobiles, has been increasing for sometime now and is expected to do the same, going forward. Replacement tyres varies across categories, due to different life-spans of tyres, which depends on

reasons like, Road condition, Load carried, Distance traveled and Re-treading.

Literature review:

A wide range of factors create customer expectations. A customer's previous experiences, the communication of an organisation with its customers, advertisements, service recovery, promises, informal recommendations, formal recommendations, price to be paid, personal needs, corporate image and sales people all influence the formation of customer expectations (Zeithaml, Parasuraman & Berry, 1990; Pitt & Jeantrout, 1994; Hart, Heskett & Sasser, 1996; Zeithaml, Berry and Parasuraman, 1993; Robledo. 2001; Teboul, 1991; Gronroos. 1984, 1990; Cadotte. Woodruff & Jenkins, 1987; Yu, 2005; Bebeko, 2000).

MacInnis and Price (1987) postulate that imagery processing and consumer experience and expertise in the product category may interact to affect purchase satisfaction. In the case of discursive processing, product experience and knowledge are related to important differences in memory and cognitive structure that affect information search and processing (Alba and Hutchinson 1987). However, almost nothing is known about the effect of consumer experience on imagery processing.

MacInnis and Price (1987) argue that a different set of conditions may operate for more experienced consumers. Because of their richer knowledge base, experienced consumers may imagine the anticipated event as unfolding in many ways. Moreover, although experienced consumers too are likely to favour positive outcomes in their imagining, their past experiences may prompt them to consider negative outcomes as well. By imagining many different outcomes, and incorporating both favorable and unfavorable outcomes, their expectations for any one event occurring are likely to be lower than those for novices. Consequently, for experienced as compared to inexperienced consumers, there is a greater probability that at least one of the imagined events will unfold as planned (compared to the single event imagined for novices). Moreover, experienced consumers incorporate into their imagery potentially negative outcomes, they may also engage in behaviors that reduce the probability that negative events will occur or affect their plans. Lowered expectations for a single positive event, along with imagery of negative events and risk reduction actions, may simultaneously reduce expectations for a single event, and increase ultimate satisfaction with the imagined event.

Examining the role of imagery processing and experience on consumer expectations and satisfaction suggests a main effect of imagery processing, and an interaction of imagery processing and consumer experience on a positivity bias in expected outcomes, confidence in expectations, expectancy-disconfirmation and satisfaction. Specifically, based on extant theory, imagery processing when combined with low levels of experience should result in more positivity bias, more expectancy-disconfirmation, and less satisfaction. In contrast, imagery processing when combined with high levels of experience should result in less of a positivity bias, less expectancy disconfirmation and more satisfaction.

Research has long established that perception of product quality can be influenced by various attributes, such as brand name (Dawar and Parker 1994; Dodds, Monroe, and Grewal 1991), Price (Dodds, Monroe, and Grewal 1991; Rao and Monroe 1989) and Product appearance (Dawar and Parker 1994). The experiment shows that the overall tyre performance is based on five factors (in order of importance) appearance, durability, ride, traction,

and handling (J.D. Power 2005) "tyre manufacturers not only need to provide better tyre performance but also need to focus on aligning strategies to customer expectations so they can provide a satisfactory tyre ownership experience". The study finds that the absence of tyre problems contributes to greater level of satisfaction and strongly influences customers perceptions of the tyre brand. Furthermore, problem-free tyre experience lead a higher degree of advocacy and loyalty for the tyre brand. Drivers of customer satisfaction and loyalty at the industry levels are – expectation, image, product quality and service quality (Anne Martensen et. al. 2000) expectation have no or only a very limited impact on satisfaction and loyalty. Image is the main drivers for customer satisfaction. Service become a more important driver for bank customer loyalty. But image still has the largest impact on loyalty. The research has shown that satisfaction for a product is also related to how customers are satisfied by their buying experience (Pettijohn CE et al. 2002). The firms marketing success generally depends on the dealers, because these persons are the ones who have the most direct influence on the customers. In this sense, estimating customers judgment about their "buying experience" and evaluating the aspects that influence their perception of this service most, could help marketing the product a success.

Objectives of the study:

Customer experience has received considerable attention from researchers in marketing. Customer experience is generally construed to be a post consumption evaluation depends on perceived quality or value, expectation, and confirmation/disconfirmation. The study is aimed at to know the impact of customers experience on replacement of tyre in Light and Heavy commercial vehicles in Chidambaram Town.

Research design:

To study the purchasing behaviour on the basis of their experience in Heavy and Light commercial vehicles owners on Replacement tyres, Quantitative research study was done as descriptive information was required over there. The researcher used survey method using schedules. The researcher personally involved in this research and collected primary data

from the respondent. The respondents are - Owners of Bus, Trucks, and Light Commercial Vehicles.

(LCV) owners and 16 percent of them are Bus owners.

Data collection tool:

Data collection instruments were developed as a part of the study's total research design to systematize the collection of data and to ensure that all the respondents are asked the same questions and in the same order. A Schedule was designed to know about the purchase behaviour of Heavy and Light commercial vehicles owners on Replacement tyres on the basis of experience. Schedule designed includes both substantive questions that are relevant to Heavy and Light commercial vehicles owners on Replacement tyres.

Table 2 - Awareness of brands in years

Awareness in years	Frequency	Percent
Up to 5 years	11	11.0
5-10 years	11	11.0
10-15 years	13	13.0
15 years & above	65	65.0

Source - Primary Data computed

Sampling and Data Collection:

The sampling plan addresses three questions: Whom to survey (the sampling unit), how many to survey (the sample size) and how to select them (the sampling procedure). The size of the sample is dependent both on the size of the budget and on the degree of confidence that the researcher wants to place in the findings. Here a sample size of 100 customers was selected throughout Chidambaram Town, Tamilnadu, India using the Stratified Random Sampling technique. Various types of data analysis tools were used to analyze the data collected by the schedule, descriptive and one way ANOVA.

Table- 2 shows the experience of the customers in various sectors of the commercial vehicles. Experience of respondent plays an important role in their purchasing behaviour of replacement tyres. Among the respondent of this study about 65 percent of the respondent having experience of 15 years. Gulorsen and Robert John (1994) examined the relative impact of four variables namely product, information availability, experience and judgment ability. They were identified as having the major influence on consumer information. They also reported that experience, information availability, interaction of product type and experience had a significant influence on the amount of search behaviour for goods.

Table 3 - Brand Awareness and Experience

Influencing Factor	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Experience	98	98.0	98.0	98.0
Friends	2	2.0	2.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source - Primary Data computed

Table - 3 shows that among the respondent 98 percent of them are aware of the brands through experience and rest of the 2 percent of the respondent are aware of the brands through friends. It shows that experience of a person place an important influencing factor to the purchase of replacement tyres.

Table 4 - Opinion towards replacement of tyres based on experience

Factor Experience	Mean	Std. Deviation
-------------------	------	----------------

Analysis and discussion:

After all the customers were surveyed, i.e., a sample size of 100, the analysis was done on the basis of their responses.

Table 1 - Type of vehicle owned

Type of Vehicle	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Bus	16	16.0	16.0	16.0
Trucks	43	43.0	43.0	59.0
LCV	41	41.0	41.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source - Primary Data computed

Table - 1 shows that among the respondent, 43 percent of the respondents are truck owners, 41 percent of them are Light Commercial Vehicle

Price 2-5 years	3.7778	.66667
5-10 years	3.7273	.64667
10-15 years	3.1538	.98710
15 years & above	3.6667	.81650
Reliability 2-5 years	2.6078	1.18454
5-10 years	3.1818	1.60114
10-15 years	3.0000	1.68325
15 years & above	3.3333	1.41421
Performance 2-5 years	2.9091	1.30035
5-10 years	3.3077	1.31559
10-15 years	2.7857	1.18831
15 years & above	3.5556	1.23603
Safety 2-5 years	2.2222	.66667
5-10 years	2.5455	1.43970
10-15 years	2.4615	1.12660
15 years & above	2.7857	1.18831
Road Grip 2-5 years	2.7451	1.26243
5-10 years	2.8182	1.40130
10-15 years	2.9231	1.44115
15 years & above	3.5556	1.50923
Depth 2-5 years	2.8182	1.40130
5-10 years	2.8235	1.28025
10-15 years	3.6154	1.38875
15 years & above	3.7778	1.39443
Rolling Resistance 2-5 years	3.0000	2.2132
5-10 years	3.4615	1.28592
10-15 years	3.2143	1.18831
15 years & above	3.6667	1.32288
Quick Availability 2-5 years	3.2222	1.30171
5-10 years	2.3636	.92442
10-15 years	2.3848	.96077
15 years & above	2.6667	1.17757
Brand already fitted 2-5 years	3.7778	1.39443
5-10 years	3.0909	1.51357
10-15 years	3.3077	1.49358
15 years & above	3.1765	1.35212

Respondents are asked to rate their purchase behaviour of Replacement of tyres based on their experience. The data are grouped based on experience and calculated mean and standard

deviation value for each factors with respect to experience. The value is displayed in the table – 4. From the mean value it is observed that buyer having experience of 2-5 years are satisfied with the price of Replacement tyres than others and they are also prefer for quick availability of Replacement tyres. Those who have more than 15 years are influenced by Reliability, Performance, Safety, Road Grip, Depth, Rolling resistance.

Findings:

From the study it is found that about 51 percent of the respondents having experience of more than 15 years. Experience of a person plays an important role of influencing factor for the purchase of replacement tyres. About 51 percent of the respondent know the brands for past 20 years and 14 percent of the respondents are heard the brand of 15-20 years, only 2 percent of the respondents are aware of the brand for 2 years. Brands already fitted shows major reason influencing the purchase behaviour of the respondent followed by the performance of tyres. And it is also found that experience is also made an impact on purchase of Replacement tyres.

Suggestions:

All level of experienced owners perceived similar level of opinion towards Replacement of tyres, it shows that, the owners are having less involvement with the purchase of replacement tyres. So, owners should be trained and create awareness towards importance of purchase in Replacement Tyres. The tyre manufacturers to invite the owners and explain the merits of the Replacement of Tyres, so it will help to capture the market share and increase sales volume.

Conclusion:

From the study it is concluded that there are different factors influencing the owners of the

Heavy and Light Commercial Vehicles in replacement tyres, among the factors experience is main factor to influence the replacement of tyres.

References:

1. Alba, Joseph W. and J. Wesley Hutchinson (1987). "Dimensions of Consumer Expertise." *Journal of Consumer Research*, 13. (March). pp 411-454.
 2. Mitchell, Deborah J. (1989). "Mental Simulation in Consumer Choice." Working Paper. Department of Marketing. The Wharton School. University of Pennsylvania.
 3. MacInnis, Deborah J. and Linda L. Price (1987). "The Role of Imagery in Information Processing: Review and Extensions." *Journal of Consumer Research*, 13 (March).pp 473-491.
 4. Deborah J. MacInnis and Linda L. Price (1990) "An Exploratory Study of the Effects of Imagery Processing and Consumer Experience on Expectations and Satisfaction". *Advances in Consumer Research*. Vol. 17. pp 41-47.
 5. J.D. Power Asia Pacific (2004) "India Original Tire Customer Satisfaction Study". J.D. Power Asia Pacific.
 6. J.D. Power and Associates (2005) "South Africa Original Equipment Tire Customer Satisfaction Index (CSI) Study". J.D. Power and Associates.
 7. Susan Chirayath, (2006) "Market Potential and Brand Perception of Apollo Tyres in Light Commercial Vehicles in the State of Jharkhand". *Icfai Journal of Management Research*, January.
 8. Philip Kotler and Kevin Lane Keller, *Marketing Management*. 12th ed. Pearson Education Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi.
 9. Dawar, Niraj and Philip Parker (1994) "Marketing Universals : Consumers use of Brand Name, Price, Physical Appearance and Retailer Reputation as signals of product Quality", *Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 58, April, pp 81-95.
 10. Dodds, William B., Kent B. Monroe, and Dhruv Grewal (1991), "Effects of Price, Brand, and Store Information on Buyers Product Evaluation". *Journal of Marketing Research*, 28 (August) pp 307-319.
 11. Rao, Akshay R and Kent B. Monroe (1989) "The Effect of Price, Brand Name, and Store name on Buyers Perceptions of Product Quality". *Journal of Marketing Research*, 26(August) pp 351-357.
 12. Gulorsen, Robert John (1994) "The Relative influence of the key factors that effect information gathering behaviour among goods and services purchasers", Saint Lous University, DAI-A 54/07, (January) pp 2653.
 13. Anne Martensen, Lars Gronholdt and Kai Kristensen (2000) "The drivers of customer satisfaction and loyalty : Cross industry findings from Denmark". *Total Quality Management*. Vol.11. Nos. 4/5&6. pp S544-S553.
 14. Rebecca J.Slotegraff and J. Jeffrey Inman. (2004) "Longitudinal shifts in the Drivers of satisfaction with product Quality; The Role of Attribute Resolvability". *Journal of Marketing Research*. Vol. XLI. August, pp 269-280.
 15. Zeithatnl V.A., Parasuraman, A. & Berry, L.L. (1990). "Guidelines for conducting service quality research". *Marketing Research*, 2(4): pp 34-44.
 16. Pitt, L.F. & Jeantrout, B. (1994). "Management of customer expectations in service firms: A study and a checklist". *The Services Industries Journal* 14(2): pp 170-189.
 17. Hart, CW. L., Heskett, J.L & Sasser, W.E. Jr. (1990). "The profitable art of service recovery". *Harvard Business Review*, 6H(4): pp 148-156.
 18. Zeithaml V.A., Berry, L.L. & Parasuraman, A. (1996). "The behavioural consequences of service quality". *Journal of Marketing*, 6Q (2) pp 31-46
 19. Robledo, M.A. (2001). "Measuring and managing service quality: integrating customer expectations". *Managing Service Quality*, 11(1) pp 22-31.
 20. Gronroos, C (1990). *Services management and marketing: Managing the moments of truth in service competition*. Lexington, M.A.: Lexington Books.
 21. Yu, L. (2005). "The great expectations effect", *MIT Sloan Management Review*, 47(D): 5.38 *S.Afr.J.Bus.Management*.
- Bebko, CP. (2000). "Service intangibility and its impact on consumer expectations of service quality". *Journal of Services Marketing*, 14(1) pp 9-26.